

Performance and degradation analysis of sputter deposited thin-film platinum cathodes in PEM water electrolyzers analyzed by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Sputter-etching modification of PEM improves performance of thin-film Pt for HER.
- Systematic study of sputtered Pt layers in range from $480 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ down to $3.7 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.
- MEA with $240 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ reached 4000 mA cm^{-2} at 2.0 V surpassing commercial reference.
- Ultra-low Pt loaded MEAs had initially high performance, but degraded rapidly.
- Comprehensive EIS analysis revealed a loss of catalytically active sites.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers (PEM-WEs) are a key technology for green hydrogen production, however their large-scale deployment has been hindered by the reliance on noble metal catalysts, such as platinum (Pt) and iridium (Ir). In this study, we present a fully dry and scalable approach for fabricating ultra-low platinum-loaded cathodes for PEM-WE using only magnetron sputtering. The process involves a two-step approach: sputter-etching pre-treatment of the PEM surface to increase the catalyst dispersion and active surface area, followed by direct sputtering of Pt. We systematically investigate Membrane Electrode Assemblies (MEAs) with Pt loadings ranging from around $3.7 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ to $480 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$, achieving significant performance improvement over the commercial electrodes, while reducing the Pt loading to half. Moreover, MEAs with Pt loadings around $20 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ exhibited excellent initial performance of approximately 2500 mA cm^{-2} , but their stability proved to be a critical challenge. Comprehensive Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) reveals key degradation mechanisms in Pt thin films, including insufficient lateral conductivity and catalyst detachment. This work provides valuable insights into the optimization of sputtered low-loading catalysts for the cathode of

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PEM-WE, and the analysis of the degradation pathways opens up a possibility to further stabilize the ultra-low catalyst loadings.

1. Introduction

The global demand for energy continues to rise, primarily met by fossil fuels, contributing to environmental degradation and climate change. To break the reliance on fossil fuels, a transition to renewable or low-emission energy sources is necessary [1]. However, renewable energy sources such as wind and solar are intermittent, requiring efficient energy storage solutions to stabilize the electricity grid [2]. The concept of the hydrogen economy is a promising solution, where hydrogen produced through electrolysis using renewable electricity serves as a clean, emission-free energy carrier and high-capacity energy storage medium. Green hydrogen has a significant potential not only for energy storage but also for applications in transport and the chemical industry, leading to a sustainable future [3–9].

In the hydrogen economy, Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers (PEM-WE) are expected to play a significant role. They offer a fast response to input changes, operate across a wide power range, achieve high current densities, and produce high purity hydrogen, which can be pressurized directly at the output of the electrolyzers [10, 11]. The major drawback of PEM-WEs lies in their dependency on the high noble metal catalysts loading, typically Ir/IrO₂ on the anode (~2.5 mg cm⁻²) and Pt on the cathode (~0.4–0.5 mg cm⁻²) [12,13]. To enable the widespread adoption of PEM-WE technology, it is imperative to reduce the amount of noble metals, thereby lowering the cost of produced hydrogen while maintaining electrolysis efficiency [14–17].

Efforts have focused on improving the anode, where the Oxygen Evolution Reaction (OER) occurs [18], and where iridium and ruthenium-based catalysts are typically used [14,15,17,19]. Meanwhile, platinum is commonly used as a catalyst for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) at the cathode. Although the demand for Pt loading is relatively lower compared to the noble metals loading on the anode side, reducing its quantity remains essential for the broader commercialization of PEM-WEs [10,17,20,21].

Commonly utilized methods for preparing catalysts with low-noble-metal-loading involve enhancing the active surface area or designing multielement systems [12,22]. A mainstream technology involving platinum nanoparticles dispersed on a carbon support has been adopted from fuel cell development [10,11]. The carbon support improves platinum utilization for catalytic reactions and it is suitable due to its electrical conductivity and low costs of preparation [13]. For instance, in Ref. [20], Pt-Co bimodal nanoparticles were fabricated on carbon paper via electrochemical deposition followed by annealing. Despite a Pt loading of 18.4 μg cm⁻², the catalyst achieved a high current density of 2390 mA cm⁻² at 1.9 V, attributed to the alloying effect. A similar preparation approach was employed in Ref. [23], where a catalyst with 21 μg_{Pt} cm⁻² achieved 1800 mA cm⁻² at 1.9 V. The influence of Pt particle size was studied in Ref. [24], revealing that while single-atom sized Pt particles were unstable under operating conditions, nanoparticles with sizes between 1 nm and 2 nm exhibited a current density of 1000 mA cm⁻² at 1.71 V using only 15 μg_{Pt} cm⁻². Recently, Pt nanoclusters dispersed on a modified carbon support achieved outstanding performance of 3000 mA cm⁻² at 1.75 V with just 20 μg_{Pt} cm⁻² [25]. In another study [26], electron beam evaporation was used to prepare a catalyst with an extremely low Pt loading of 3.7 μg cm⁻², reaching 500 mA cm⁻² at 1.64 V. Notably, this method is conceptually similar to the magnetron sputtering technique employed in this paper. These state-of-the-art examples highlight that substantial platinum savings are indeed possible without sacrificing performance, since the results are compared to conventional high-loading references [20,26].

The typical (“wet”) preparation procedure for catalytic layers in electrolyzers demands multiple chemical reactions, additional

substances, and heating to higher temperatures to ensure particle adhesion to the membrane in the desired form [27–31]. In contrast, magnetron sputtering is a relatively simple, completely “dry” approach, which can be easily scaled up and commercialized [32]. This method enables the precise deposition of well-defined and reproducible thin catalytic layers onto the Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) without the need for precursors for nanoparticle synthesis or chemical reactions [33–39]. Previous studies [40–42] have shown that sputter-etching treatment of the PEM enhances the performance of the Membrane Electrode Assembly (MEA) in the electrolyzer. In this process, CeO_x is sputtered onto the membrane in a working atmosphere containing reactive oxygen, creating a fiber-like structure [42]. Consequently, this structure increases the surface area available for catalyst deposition, leading to higher catalyst utilization. The sputter-etching treatment enables the elimination of support particles and ensures better ionomer-catalyst interconnection on the anodic side of the PEM-WE [43], while maintaining the catalyst performance. However, this treatment has not yet been thoroughly tested on the cathode side of PEM-WE, where a similar effect can be anticipated. Consequently, it may allow us to efficiently prepare high performance catalyst coated membrane, using a single vacuum entry to deposit the catalytic layer for both the anode and cathode of the PEM-WE, greatly simplifying and streamlining the whole process.

Since HER is the faster and less catalytically demanding reaction than OER under the PEM-WE conditions, it is expected that much lower noble metal loadings can be utilized while retaining satisfactory performance. In this study, we investigate the performance and stability of the low-Pt loading catalysts (down to several μg cm⁻²) for PEM-WE. We find the sweet spot between Pt loading, activity, and stability. Our detailed Potentiostatic Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (PEIS) analysis reveals that the rapid degradation of low-Pt-loading catalysts originates from insufficient lateral connectivity, disconnection of active sites and change in the chemical state of the catalyst. This information is crucial for further reduction of the Pt loading on the cathode of PEM-WE, since it allows deciphering the degradation mechanisms, which is crucial for their future mitigation and improvement of the overall performance of the low-Pt loading PEM-WEs.

2. Methods

2.1. MEA preparation

The 50.8 μm thick Nafion™ NR 212 proton exchange membrane (Chemours) was used for all samples. On the anode side, a thin layer of pure metallic iridium, 50 nm thick (113 μg_{Ir} cm⁻²), was sputtered directly from a 2-inch target (99.99 %, K. J. Lesker) using a TORUS balanced magnetron (K. J. Lesker). The sputtering process was carried out at a pressure of 0.5 Pa in an argon atmosphere (Linde, 99.9999 %), flowing at a rate of 7 sccm. The direct current (DC) source DC01BP (K. J. Lesker) provided a sputtering power of 1.48 W cm⁻², and the deposition lasted for 32 min.

The sintered micrograined Ti Porous Transport Layer (PTL) from Mott was used on the anode, previously coated on both sides with 50 nm of Pt for corrosion protection.

While the anode configuration remained constant, the cathode varied. A commercial Gas Diffusion Electrode (GDE) from Fuel Cell Store (carbon paper GDE 0.5 mg cm⁻² PtC 60 %), containing 0.5 mg cm⁻² Pt was used as a reference. All other cathode catalyst layers were prepared using magnetron sputtering or sputter-etching process. The sputter-etching treatment utilized optimal parameters as described in Ref. [42], involving CeO₂ target (99.99 %, K. J. Lesker, 4-inch)

sputtering in a reactive argon-oxygen atmosphere (15 sccm of Ar (Linde, 99.999 %), 0.23 sccm of O₂ (Linde, 99.995 %)) for 70 min at a pressure of 0.4 Pa. The base pressure before sputtering was on the order of 10⁻⁵ Pa. For the sputter-etching treatment, the CESAR® RF generator (13.56 MHz) coupled with a NAVIO™ impedance matching device (both from Advanced Energy) was used to sputter form the non-conductive CeO₂ target, with the power set at 0.80 W cm⁻².

Subsequently, platinum was sputtered from a 4-inch target (99.99 %, Safina) onto the modified membrane, with variations in the sputtering time, resulting in different catalyst loadings. The working pressure was 0.5 Pa in an argon atmosphere at a flow rate of 15 sccm. The Pt sputtering was performed at least from the base pressure of 5.10⁻⁴ Pa to ensure the metallic state of Pt. The power was set at 0.49 W cm⁻² using the same power source as for the previous DC deposition.

Platinum loadings ranged from 3.7 μg cm⁻² (1.7 nm thickness) to 480 μg cm⁻² (224 nm of Pt). The Pt thicknesses on the fiber-like sputter-etched membrane correspond to the equivalent thickness on the flat substrate, as they can vary due to the complex morphology of the system. The morphologies of the sputter-etched and consequently Pt-coated membranes of various Pt loadings, captured using scanning electron microscope (SEM), are depicted in Fig. S1 in Supplementary Information (SI). The next three membranes were prepared without the sputter-etching treatment using the same conditions for Pt sputter deposition (i.e. PEMs in MEA GDE, MEA 480 μg plain and MEA 120 μg plain). The full description and labelling of the prepared samples, used from here onward, is given in Table 1.

For all membranes with sputtered catalyst layer, the Gas Diffusion Layer (GDL) with microporous layer without Pt (Sigracet 29 BC) was used as a PTL on the cathode.

The area of the PTLs and catalyst layers was always a square with a size of 2.15 cm, resulting in a geometric active area of 4.62 cm². The thickness of the sputtered layers was determined by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) using the varnish droplet method on a flat surface [44].

2.2. Single-cell electrolyzer measurements

All MEAs were tested for at least four days in a water electrolyzer single cell in a dedicated testing station (TP-5, Greenlight Innovation). The MEAs were placed between bipolar plates and pressurized at 8 bar. The temperature of the plates was controlled by a Selec PID500 thermostat, consistently held at 80 °C. High-purity deionized water (18.2 MΩ cm at 25 °C) was delivered via a BT100M peristaltic pump at a flow rate of 33 ml min⁻¹, with a Swagelok solid particle filter ensuring clean supply. Voltage was controlled using a SP-150 potentiostat coupled with a 20 A current booster (BioLogic) using the four-probe method for accurate measurements. The parameters of individual measurement parts were controlled using EC-Lab software.

The main parts of the procedure were set as follows – a staircase

Table 1

The complete list of prepared membranes. The mass in the name of each MEA corresponds to loading of the catalyst per cm².

Name in text	Sputtered Pt layer thickness [nm]	Cathode Pt loading [μg cm ⁻²]	PEM cathode side	Anode Ir loading [μg cm ⁻²]	PEM anode side
MEA 480 μg	224	480	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 240 μg	112	240	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 120 μg	56	120	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 60 μg	28	60	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 30 μg	14	30	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 15 μg	7	15	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 7.5 μg	3.5	7.5	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 3.7 μg	1.7	3.7	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 0 μg	0	0	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA GDE	—	500	plain	113	plain
MEA 480 μg plain	224	480	plain	113	plain
MEA 120 μg plain	56	120	plain	113	plain
MEA 240 μg v2	112	240	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 7.5 μg v2	3.5	7.5	sputter-etched	113	plain
MEA 7.5 μg v3	3.5	7.5	sputter-etched	113	plain

voltage for IV curve measurement in the staircase voltage regime (ranging from 1.7 V to 1.3, then to 2.0 V, and back to 1.3 V, with 5 mV steps for 10 s each), followed by Potentiostatic Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (PEIS), and switching voltages between 1.6 V and 1.7 V for 5 min each in the constant voltage regime, a total of 20 times. This whole sequence was repeated three times and followed by a long-term stability measurement at 1.7 V for 8 h, resulting in a total procedure duration of approximately 24 h. The procedure is the same as that described in Ref. [45] and is graphically depicted in Fig. S2.

2.3. PEIS analysis

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) is a powerful technique for studying electrochemical systems and electrode interfaces. By analyzing impedance spectra, different phenomena in the system can be separated, leading to a deeper understanding of the underlying processes. Due to its non-invasive nature, EIS serves as a valuable diagnostic tool in PEM-WEs [46–48].

The most fundamental application of EIS is the determination of ohmic resistance [47,49]. However, recent studies have increasingly focused on fitting and interpreting the entire spectra using the Equivalent Electrical Circuit (EEC) [50–55]. This work presents a significantly larger dataset of electrolyzer parameters obtained by EIS, covering variations in voltage, catalyst loading, and time evolution. Such a comprehensive dataset allows for a more precise correlation between observed impedance features and specific system processes.

The PEIS was conducted using 11 DC voltages, ranging from 1.35 V to 1.55 V in 0.02 V increments. The amplitude of AC voltage was 5 mV. The frequency range spanned from 200 kHz to 500 mHz, divided into 15 steps per decade with logarithmic spacing. Each data point was acquired over a duration of two periods with a dedicated BioLogic drift correction mode switched on.

Data processing was performed using Relaxis3 software. The spectra were fitted with a double Randles circuit (Fig. S3), where one parallel block represents the anode and the other represents the cathode (as in Ref. [46]). Each block consists of a resistor representing the charge transfer resistance of the electrode and a Constant Phase Element (CPE), which approximates the electrochemical double layer capacitance [56, 57]. An additional series resistor accounts for the ohmic resistance of the system. The frequency range for each spectrum was carefully chosen to omit the noisy and uninterpretable parts of the spectra.

Brug's formula [56,58] was used to calculate the capacitance *C* of the electrode double layer:

$$C = \frac{1}{Q\alpha R_{ct}^{\alpha}}$$

here, *Q* and *α* are parameters describing the CPE, and *R_{ct}* is the charge transfer resistance in the same Randles circuit together with the CPE.

2.4. Scanning electron microscopy

For morphological study of the sputter-etched membranes, a Mira III scanning electron microscope (TESCAN ORSAY HOLDING, a.s.) was used. The pictures in Fig. S1 are captured in the secondary electron mode with the primary beam energy of 10 keV.

3. Results and discussion

The results are presented in two main parts: In the first part, we present the performance dependency of the PEM-WE based on the Pt loading and the treatment of the PEM membrane. In the second part, we present a detailed PEIS analysis of the degradation of the low-Pt-loading PEM-WE cathodes along with suggestions for possible mitigation strategies.

3.1. Performance in the electrolyzer single-cell

In order to reduce the platinum content compared to commercial electrodes, all MEAs had cathode loadings less than or equal to $500 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$, which corresponds to the commercial GDE used as a reference.

3.1.1. Effect of sputter-etching treatment on performance

Our first goal was to verify the effect of the sputter-etching treatment on the PEM-WE cathode. We therefore prepared three MEAs with comparable loadings of approximately $500 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ (*MEA GDE*, *MEA 480 μg plain*, *MEA 480 μg* in Table 1). From the performance evaluation during the IV curves (Fig. 1), the *MEA GDE* demonstrated the highest current densities at 2.0 V (3600 A cm^{-2}), closely followed by the *MEA 480 μg* , with the *MEA 480 μg plain* performing significantly worse. This indicates that a thick Pt layer sputter-deposited on the non-etched membrane does not work well. We expect that the *MEA 480 μg plain* reached the mass transport limit region of its IV curve at lower voltages, suggesting a lower porosity of the catalyst layer.

The next step was to reduce the loading of the magnetron sputtered layers in order to find an optimal thickness for the Pt layer which would not cause the mass transport limitations, while maintaining high performance. To address this issue, an MEA with loading of $240 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ (*MEA 240 μg* with 112 nm of Pt on sputter-etched membrane) was prepared and measured in the station. This MEA outperformed not only the two sputtered samples with higher loading, but even the commercial *MEA GDE* in terms of maximal performance at higher potentials (Fig. 1),

Fig. 1. Best IV curves for *MEA 480 μg plain*, *MEA 480 μg* , *MEA GDE* and *MEA 240 μg* . Despite an identical platinum loading, *MEA 480 μg plain* exhibited worse performance than its sputter-etched counterpart, *MEA 480 μg* . Both of these samples were surpassed by the *MEA GDE*, which contained a commercial GDE with similar Pt loading. Notably, the highest performance was achieved by *MEA 240 μg* with only half the amount of Pt.

which supports previous hypotheses regarding porosity. In addition, as shown in the following section in Fig. 3, the stability during the measurement of *MEA 240 μg* was superior to that of the other membranes. This sample overcame the commercial *MEA GDE* with only half the amount of platinum (i.e., $240 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$). To ensure the reproducibility of this result and to avoid any errors in its preparation, another MEA with identical parameters (*MEA 240 μg v2*) was prepared. Its IV curves were very similar to those of the previous one, indicating that our preparation method involving membrane sputter-etching followed by Pt sputter deposition is reproducible with high precision (Fig. S4). However, for both samples, small fluctuations in current were observed. These current drops occurred randomly in time, independently of any specific voltage. The origin of these changes might come from bubble formation. These samples showed the highest gas production, therefore formation lots of bubbles, that may have disturbed connectivity or blocked the active sites. As these effects were not observed at low currents, the PEIS analysis is not influenced.

3.1.2. Effect of platinum loading on performance

This result raises the question of whether we can prepare functional MEAs with even lower platinum loadings using magnetron sputtering. The positive influence of the sputter etching on the performance was also confirmed by another set of membranes with the loading of $120 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, where sputter-etching led to the significant increase in performance (Fig. S5). To determine the limits of the sputter-etching method for the preparation of the cathode catalyst layer, a series of samples with Pt loadings ranging from $120 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ down to $3.7 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ was prepared. Following the aforementioned outcomes, all of these samples had platinum sputtered onto the sputter-etched membrane to work as a cathode catalyst. As depicted in Fig. 2, the maximum current densities in the electrolyzer exhibited an overall increase with higher catalyst loading, with two exceptions – the *MEA 120 μg* performed worse compared to the *MEA 60 μg* , and the *MEA 15 μg* performed better than the *MEA 30 μg* at higher potentials. We do not attribute this behavior solely to the catalyst itself, but rather to a slight inconsistency in the actual MEA assembly.

The performance of the membranes tested evolved over the measurement period. The first day was part of the break-in process and the samples typically reached their highest current densities on the second day. Membranes with higher loadings tended to reach their best performance later than those with lower platinum thickness. Therefore, in order to compare different MEAs, we plotted the IV curve data with the highest current densities at high potentials in Fig. 2.

For membranes with lower platinum content, the performance decreased with decreasing loading. For MEAs with loadings in range from $60 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ to $3.7 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ this decrease is nearly logarithmic relative to the platinum loading. The *MEA 30 μg* performed slightly worse than expected showing only a small increase in the current density at the high voltages (e.g. 1.9 V and 2.0 V, Fig. S6), suggesting severe mass transport limitations. However, after several cycles, the IV curves of this MEA returned to a concave shape, and the limitation was resolved. A similar but less pronounced effect was observed in all of the samples. During the first two days, the IV curves displayed a convex shape at higher voltages. Over time, this characteristic disappeared, and the curves became concave over the entire measurement range. This may explain the break in the performance-loading trend in Fig. 2 for the *MEA 30 μg* vs. *MEA 15 μg* .

In the high Pt loading range (from 60 to $480 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$), the increase in peak current becomes less pronounced compared to lower-loading samples. This indicates that for higher-loading MEAs, the amount of platinum is not so crucial for maximal performance in the electrolyzer, and presumably not all of platinum is effectively utilized for the HER. We hypothesize that the lower performance of *MEA 480 μg* compared to the *MEA 240 μg* is likely due to mass transport limitations caused by the excessive thickness of the Pt layer. All of these effects are more evident on lower voltages (around 1.7 V).

Fig. 2. Best achieved performance of all sputter-etched membranes. For MEAs with loading below $60 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, the achieved current densities increased logarithmically with increasing Pt loading. For higher-loading samples, the current densities were more similar.

We have determined the optimal Pt loading for achieving the best performance in the testing station. However, as our objective is to minimize the use of Pt, there may be a different optimal loading that prioritizes the ratio of performance-to-noble-metal-loading. By plotting the highest current density achieved, normalized by the total loading of Pt and Ir loading (specific current density), we observed that the maximum shifts towards membranes with lower loadings (Fig. S7), specifically to the MEA with Pt loading of $15 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ (corresponding to $130 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of total noble metal loading).

To ensure reproducibility of the preparation approach also in the low-Pt-loading range, the MEA $7.5 \mu\text{g v2}$ and MEA $7.5 \mu\text{g v3}$ were measured as identical samples to the MEA $7.5 \mu\text{g}$. As in case of high-loading pair MEA $240 \mu\text{g}$ and MEA $240 \mu\text{g v2}$, we observed very similar IV curves, confirming good reproducibility of our measurement (Fig. S8).

3.1.3. Stability evolution

After reaching their maximal performance, the current densities of the tested samples began to decline. For the three membranes with higher platinum loading (MEA $480 \mu\text{g}$, MEA $480 \mu\text{g plain}$ and MEA GDE), the decrease in performance was comparable. However, a more pronounced degradation was observed for the MEA $120 \mu\text{g}$. While this MEA initially showed almost twice the performance of the MEA $120 \mu\text{g plain}$, its current density dropped to a similar level after four days. Although the sputter-etching treatment initially enhanced the activity, it did not contribute to sustained stability. Noted, on the second day of MEA $120 \mu\text{g}$ testing, a water leakage caused starvation, which may have influenced the subsequent measurements.

Membranes with a Pt thickness below 100 nm ($200 \mu\text{gPt cm}^{-2}$) experienced a significant decrease in performance over the measuring period. Over the three days after reaching peak performance, their current densities dropped to 40 % of their maximal values (Fig. 3). In contrast, the samples with high Pt loading exhibited a much slower degradation. The relative performance loss was more pronounced at lower voltages (e.g. 1.5 V), while at 2.0 V, the current decreased by only 30 % (Fig. S9). This can be attributed to the different regions of the IV curve: at lower voltages, performance is dominated by electrode kinetics, where at higher voltages, ohmic resistance becomes the main limiting factor. If the exchange current density decreases significantly but ohmic resistance remains relatively stable, the relative performance drop appears less severe at higher voltages. However, after correcting for ohmic losses using values determined from subsequent PEIS analysis, the degradation behavior becomes nearly identical across all voltages (Fig. S10). All the IV curves are shown in Fig. S11.

Fig. 3. Time evolution of current densities normalized to their maximal value, showing the relative rate of degradation for each MEA. Cycle 1 in this graph is a cycle with the best performance of each MEA. All data were measured at 1.5 V. While the MEA $480 \mu\text{g}$, and especially the MEA $240 \mu\text{g}$, exhibited relatively stable performance, all membranes with lower Pt loading experienced rapid degradation.

3.1.4. Summary of the performance evaluation

The sputter-etching procedure applied to the cathode side of the membrane showed a positive effect on the electrolyzer's performance. This method allowed half the amount of Pt to be used while exceeding the performance of the commercial GDE. Moreover, low Pt loadings sputtered onto sputter-etched membranes achieved current densities comparable to high-loading MEAs, as performance does not decrease linearly with reduced Pt loading but follows a logarithmic trend. For instance, while the MEA $240 \mu\text{g}$ contained 16 times more platinum than the MEA $15 \mu\text{g}$, its maximum current density was only 1.8 times higher. This finding is significant in the context of reducing platinum usage.

On the other hand, the samples with Pt thicknesses below $200 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ showed poor stability. It is possible that the platinum particles began to agglomerate or were washed off the membrane, resulting in a loss of lateral conductivity or a decrease of the active surface area [41, 59–61]. To maintain the high activity of the Pt thin layers, the causes of this degradation need to be identified and addressed. A detailed analysis was therefore carried out, focusing primarily on PEIS data.

3.2. PEIS analysis

3.2.1. Influence of sputter-etching modification of PEM to PEIS data

Firstly, we compare the parameters of sputter-etched and plain (unetched) pairs of membranes, starting with the pair containing $480 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of Pt. Between the first and second cycle, a significant decrease in ohmic resistance is observed for the MEA $480 \mu\text{g plain}$, while no similar change is detected for the sputter-etched MEA $480 \mu\text{g}$ (Fig. S12). Initially, the Pt layer on the non-etched membrane may be so thick that it blocks pathways for hydrogen to diffuse through, resulting in a blocking of the active Pt sites by the gas. After break-in in the second day, there is a moderate increase in ohmic resistance for both MEAs, with the sputter-etched one exhibiting slightly higher values. Therefore, the sputter-etching treatment appears to enhance performance through mechanisms other than simply reducing the membrane thickness (which is merely in units of μm), which would result in lower ohmic resistance [47]. A similar trend is observed for a pair of plain and sputter-etched MEAs with Pt loading of $120 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ (Fig. S13). In conclusion, ohmic resistance does not explain the superior performance of sputter-etched MEAs.

The increased ohmic resistance observed in sputter-etched membranes may stem from poorer electrical connectivity between the GDL and the platinum layer [62], where a smaller portion of the catalyst is in direct contact with the GDL. Some platinum regions may even lack any

electrical connection to the GDL. Another possible factor is residual CeO_x from the sputter-etching process. As CeO_x is non-conductive and may not dissolve on the cathode, it could further hinder electrical conductivity. On the other hand, the sputter-etching treatment is expected to enhance the contact area at the membrane-catalyst interface, which should result in higher capacitance and reduced charge transfer resistance compared to non-etched membranes.

Capacitance can serve as a useful parameter strongly correlated with the electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) of the electrode-electrolyte interface [63–66]. A higher capacitance could imply a larger interface surface area. On the contrary to the conventional methods of ECSA assessment, it allows the measurements *operando*, without changing or modifying the measurement setup by gases flushing [67]. For the cathodes, the sputter-etched membranes exhibited approximately five times higher capacitance than their plain counterparts, despite the catalyst loading being the same (Fig. S14). This supports the hypothesis [42] that sputter-etching increases the membrane surface area and improves the interconnection between the ionomer and the catalyst. Nevertheless, the ratio of capacitances between sputter-etched and plain membranes does not directly match the ratio of their performances, indicating that the performance is not solely determined by the double-layer capacitance. We hypothesize that the sputter-etched morphology additionally facilitates more efficient removal of hydrogen gas from the catalyst layer, thereby mitigating the mass transport limitations that are prominent in the dense, non-etched Pt layers.

Ohmic resistance is a key parameter in PEM electrolyzers, as it contributes significantly to losses at higher currents, where polarization resistance is negligible [10,49,68]. This parameter can be readily obtained from the EIS spectrum as the intersection of the Nyquist plot data with the real axis [47]. Its value depends on the thickness of the membrane, its conductivity, and the cell hardware, as well as on the connections between the GDL, the catalyst layer, and the membrane [49,62,69]. To minimize the latter, high lateral conductivity is essential.

Membranes with thinner Pt catalyst layers may lack sufficient lateral conductivity when sputtered onto a sputter-etched membrane [41]. We observe an increase in ohmic resistance with decreasing platinum loading (Fig. S15) immediately after cell assembly (in cycle 1), before any significant long-time operation of the electrolyzer, indicating that degradation has not yet impacted these values. The lowest ohmic resistance was observed for the MEA 240 μg ; however, for loadings between 20 $\mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and 500 $\mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$, the resistance was only marginally higher. A notable increase occurs for membranes with Pt loadings lower than 20 $\mu\text{g} \text{cm}^{-2}$ (i.e. thickness of 10 nm), suggesting that such thin layers may not provide adequate lateral conductivity/connectivity on sputter-etched membranes or that the catalyst does not simply cover the whole area of the sputter-etched PEM surface. This can be supported by the SEM images presented in Fig. S1, where we see that a thicker layer of platinum leads to better lateral percolation in between the individual fibers on the cathode side of the MEAs with higher Pt loading even before being pressed together within the single cell.

Over time, as the degradation of the catalyst layer progressed, the ohmic resistance increased in all membranes except of the MEA 240 μg , with values rising by at least 50 %, and in some cases by more than 100 %. This indicates a loss of lateral conductivity, or possibly even catalyst loss (Fig. 4). Despite this trend, the ohmic resistance of the MEA 240 μg decreased over the measurement period, improving its performance. This reduction is the main reason why this sample outperformed the MEA GDE. In the activation region of the polarization curves, the MEA GDE shows higher performance than the MEA 240 μg , however, the lower ohmic resistance in the MEA 240 μg results in higher current densities at higher potentials (Fig. S16).

While the increase in ohmic resistance in sub-200 μg_{Pt} MEAs is significant, it is not the primary cause of their performance degradation. Even after correction for ohmic losses, the performance declines over the

Fig. 4. Time evolution of ohmic resistance at voltage of 1.39 V. All membranes experienced an increase in ohmic resistance over time, except for MEA 240 μg . The overall increase in ohmic resistance supports the hypothesis about the loss of active Pt sites.

measurement period (Fig. S17). Moreover, the loss of current density (Fig. 3 and Fig. S9) is more pronounced at lower voltages in the activation region, where ohmic losses have minimal impact, indicating that the degradation cannot be explained by increased ohmic resistance alone.

Deactivation of some catalyst regions as a cause of degradation could be assessed via the evolution of the double-layer capacitance [63,66]. Using Brug's formula, we calculated the capacitance for both the anode and cathode double layers. After assembly (cycle 1), the cathode capacitance increased with higher Pt loading, following a linear trend on a log-log scale (Fig. 5). This trend was fitted using a linear function, resulting in a capacitance-loading relation expressed as $C_c = 0.013m^{1.13}$, where C_c is the cathodic capacitance and m is the Pt loading. Since the exponent is close to 1, we suggest a linear dependence of capacitance on catalyst loading. The change in capacitance is much more significant between different membranes than between different voltages, so values averaged over all voltages are plotted. In addition, the exponent remained relatively stable throughout the measurement period.

Double-layer capacitance is often used as an indicator of ECSA [63–66]. As the capacitance increases linearly with loading, a similar trend can be expected for the active area, suggesting efficient catalyst dispersion over the entire range studied. This implies that all the

Fig. 5. Cathode and anode capacitance as a function of Pt loading shown on a log-log scale for the first cycle. As the anode side was identical in all MEAs, its capacitance remained constant and almost independent of the cathode Pt loading. The cathodic capacitance spanned nearly three orders of magnitude and exhibited a linear trend on the log-log scale with an exponent of 1.13, indicating an almost direct proportionality to the platinum loading.

Fig. 6. Time evolution of cathodic capacitance at 1.43 V, where faradaic processes are less significant, and the data points exhibit relatively small error bars. The values are normalized to the maximum for each sample to facilitate comparison between samples. For samples with Pt loading below $100 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, an initial increase is observed during the break-in period, followed by a subsequent decrease, further supporting the hypothesis of active site loss.

deposited catalyst contributes to the capacitance, indicating the potential for higher Pt loadings to further improve reaction kinetics and MEA performance. However, in our case, MEA performance does not scale directly with cathodic capacitance. While the capacitance spans three orders of magnitude, the corresponding increase in performance is much less pronounced.

The degradation of low-Pt-loading MEAs over time is clearly reflected in their capacitance behavior. In all samples with Pt loading below $100 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, an initial increase in cathode capacitance—associated with break-in and catalyst activation—was followed by a decline of approximately 20–60 % from the peak value, suggesting catalyst detachment or other degradation processes (Fig. 6). In contrast, for higher-loading samples, the impedance spectra showed overlapping anodic and cathodic features, making it difficult to accurately track the time evolution of cathode capacitance due to limited spectral resolution.

Anode capacitance values vary minimally with different cathode loadings, as the anode preparation method remained the same (Fig. 5). While the cathode capacitance increases by almost three orders of magnitude, the anode capacitance varies by only half an order and remains stable over time. Thus, variations in cathode design do not affect the anodic capacitance behavior.

3.2.2. Charge transfer resistance and Tafel slope of sputter-etched MEAs

Our model of the system consists of an ohmic resistance and two electrodes, assuming a common logarithmic increase in overpotential with increasing current to describe the kinetics of each electrode (Eq. S (1)) [70–72]. The charge transfer resistance R for both reactions (where the subscripts c , a denote the cathode and anode, respectively) is defined as [73]:

$$R_c = \frac{d\eta_c}{dj} = \frac{b_c}{j \ln 10}, R_a = \frac{d\eta_a}{dj} = \frac{b_a}{j \ln 10},$$

where η represents the overpotential for each electrode, j is the current density passing through the electrolyzer, and b is the Tafel slope [74] describing the kinetics of each reaction. Consequently, plotting $1/R$ against j should give a linear dependence with a slope of $\ln 10/b$. By fitting these data, we can independently determine the Tafel slope for both the cathode and the anode (Fig. S18). In contrast, analysis of the IV curve yields only the sum of both cathodic and anodic Tafel Slopes (Fig. S19).

Fig. 7 illustrates the time evolution of the cathodic Tafel slope. Its values remain relatively stable for the MEA $240 \mu\text{g}$ and the MEA $480 \mu\text{g}$. In contrast, a significant increase is observed for the membranes with lower platinum loading, starting around the fifth cycle. The final Tafel slope values are almost twice as high as their initial values. These

Fig. 7. Time evolution of the cathodic Tafel slopes. Only MEAs with high Pt loading (above $200 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$) maintained stable cathodic Tafel slopes values. In contrast, all other samples demonstrated a significant increase, suggesting either a change in the chemical state of the catalyst or a loss of active catalytic sites.

changes suggest variations in the chemical state of the catalyst [74], indicating that the pronounced degradation in thin catalytic layers is at least partially driven by catalyst chemistry.

Conversely, no substantial changes are observed in the anodic Tafel slope values (Fig. S20). The sum of the anodic and cathodic Tafel slopes closely matches the Tafel slope obtained by fitting the ohmic-drop corrected IV curve (Fig. S21), confirming the consistency of the analysis.

The determination of the Tafel slope for the MEA $3.7 \mu\text{g}$ and the MEA $7.5 \mu\text{g}$ is significantly more complex. The data points of $1/R_c(j)$ do not align along a single linear trend but instead form two distinct linear regions with a sharp transition between them (Fig. S22). This indicates the presence of two different reaction regimes, each characterized by a different Tafel slope. At low current densities, the Tafel slope remains relatively low, with values comparable to those of higher-loading membranes, around the typical Pt value of 30 mV dec^{-1} [75,76]. However, at higher currents, the Tafel slope exceeds 100 mV dec^{-1} or more. Similar behavior has been already reported in the literature [77, 78].

This dual-regime behavior is observed for the four MEAs with the lowest Pt loadings, i.e. the MEA $3.7 \mu\text{g}$, the MEA $7.5 \mu\text{g}$, the MEA $15 \mu\text{g}$, and the MEA $30 \mu\text{g}$. For the latter two, the previously reported Tafel slopes represented an average over both regimes, as the transition between them was less pronounced. However, fitting the data using two linear segments provides a more accurate representation of their behavior.

We hypothesize that at low currents, proton reduction is predominantly catalyzed by platinum atoms, resulting in a relatively low Tafel slope. As voltage and current increase, the available Pt sites become insufficient to sustain the reaction, and hydrogen evolution starts to occur on other materials, such as carbon in the GDL. These alternative materials exhibit significantly lower catalytic activity and the mechanism of the HER is different, resulting in a much higher Tafel slope [76, 79].

This observation provides an insight into the minimum platinum loading required for an electrolyzer. Since the goal is to achieve the lowest possible overpotential at a given current, the system should operate in the low Tafel slope regime over the widest possible current range. From Fig. 8, it is evident that the current at which the transition between these two regimes occurs (transition current density j_{trans}) increases with higher platinum loading. If no clear transition between the two regimes is observed, it indicates that sufficient platinum is present on the cathode, and the rate-determining step of the electrolyzer is no longer the hydrogen evolution reaction.

Building on this, the previous statement about changes in the chemical state of the catalyst can be extended to suggest that the

Fig. 8. Time evolution of the transition current. This quantity was overall higher for MEAs with higher Pt loading, and decreased over time, reflecting the impact of degradation processes.

observed increase in Tafel slope may also result from the loss of active Pt sites. As platinum sites become unavailable, hydrogen evolution shifts to less efficient materials, and the measured Tafel slope reflects an averaged contribution from both processes.

3.2.3. Summary of the PEIS analysis

PEIS analysis of the entire membrane series allowed us to distinguish between processes occurring on the anodic and cathodic sides. The sputter-etched cathode exhibited higher capacitance than its non-etched counterpart at the same Pt loading. As the capacitance was later shown to scale linearly with Pt loading, this proves that sputter-etching treatment enlarges the active surface area. In contrast, the sputter-etched membranes exhibited higher ohmic resistance.

The ohmic resistance also showed a dependence on catalyst loading. It remained relatively stable at most loadings but increased significantly below $20 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$, likely due to reduced lateral conductivity. Additionally, the ohmic resistance increased over time, correlating with the performance loss. However, this effect alone does not completely explain the observed decline in performance. We observed a linear relationship between capacitance and Pt loading, suggesting good catalyst dispersion within the sputter-etched structure. Despite this, the overall system performance followed a different trend. This discrepancy may be explained by the fact that the performance is not solely driven by the cathodic side; instead, the slower anodic reaction is likely to play a dominant role, limiting the impact of the cathodic active area once the Pt loading is sufficiently high.

By analyzing the charge transfer resistances, we were able to separately determine the Tafel slopes for the anodic and cathodic reactions within a single cell. At the start of the measurement, most of the samples exhibited cathodic Tafel slopes close to the literature values for Pt catalysts. However, these values remained stable only for the *MEA 240 μg* and the *MEA 480 μg* , while increasing for all the other membranes.

There are two possible explanations for this effect. First, the Tafel slope is linked to the chemical state of the catalyst, suggesting structural or compositional changes in the platinum over time. Second, as some Pt active sites are being disconnected, the remaining Pt is insufficient to catalyze all the protons arriving from the anode, forcing hydrogen evolution to occur on less efficient catalytic materials. This results in an overall increase in the cathodic Tafel slope. This hypothesis is consistent with our observation in low-loading MEAs, where a lower Tafel slope is maintained at low current densities but it is much higher at higher currents. The transition between these two regimes shifts to higher currents for the membranes with higher Pt loadings, indicating that with more platinum available, the MEA can sustain more hydrogen evolution at a more favorable platinum Tafel slope. Over time, this transition

current decreases, as catalyst detachment reduces the number of active Pt sites, further limiting reaction efficiency.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we have successfully utilized sputter-etching treatment followed by Pt catalyst sputter deposition to produce cathode catalyst layers in PEM-WE. It demonstrates the feasibility of producing high-performance MEAs solely using magnetron sputtering, which is an easily scalable method. The sputter-etched membranes outperformed their non-etched counterparts in terms of both performance and stability. To explore the full potential of this method, a comprehensive series of sputter-etched membranes with varying Pt loading was prepared and tested. Notably, the *MEA 240 μg* surpassed the performance of a GDE with twice the Pt content. Even membranes with Pt loadings down to $15 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ exhibited promising performance, indicating the possibility of ultra-low-Pt-loading MEAs, although their stability remained a challenge as performance degraded over several days.

A deeper insight into the degradation mechanisms was gained through PEIS analysis performed on a real operating electrolyzer single cell. The higher capacitance observed for the sputter-etched membranes compared to the plain ones confirmed that the enhanced performance is attributed to an enlarged active surface area, despite a potentially higher ohmic resistance. The ohmic resistance is significantly increased below a loading of $20 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ due to reduced lateral conductivity. Capacitance exhibited an almost linear dependence on Pt loading across the entire range of the membranes prepared, indicating good catalyst dispersion in the sputter-etched structure.

Performance degradation is correlated with increasing ohmic resistance and reducing capacitance. We attributed these changes to the loss of active sites caused by catalyst detachment, disconnection, or particle agglomeration. In addition, we demonstrated a method to separately determine for the anodic and cathodic Tafel slopes from the charge transfer resistances, revealing two distinct HER regimes for ultra-low-Pt-loading membranes. This work provides valuable insights into the optimization of Pt utilization in PEM electrolyzers from both a practical and scientific perspective, and the performed comprehensive analyzes may lead to further improvements and enhanced stabilization of Pt layers, paving the way for more cost-effective and sustainable hydrogen production technologies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

J. Herman: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **T. Hrbek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **P. Kúš:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **I. Matolínová:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.237947>.

Data availability

The data are available at DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15281568.

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